

The Indian Chemical Society and its Journal[†]

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Distinguished dignitaries on the dais, colleagues, friends and students,

I heartily welcome you all to the Inaugural Session of this Annual Convention of Chemists.

May I take this opportunity to thank the Fellows of the Indian Chemical Society for electing me the President, and I greet all the Fellows of the Society most sincerely.

At the very outset, I pay my respectful homage to our past President Late Professor T. R. Govindachari and to our past Vice-President Late Professor R. C. Paul who contributed significantly to the cause of the chemical research and education in our country, and also to the other Fellows who left us forever recently.

Being at the Headquarters it has been my good fortune to have been involved in the welfare of the Society for a considerable period of time in the capacity of all the Office Bearers' positions, and I have always been guided by a keen desire to be worthy of the trust reposed by the Fellows in me. In fact, the welfare of the Society will remain as my mission for the rest of my life also. I would like to thank various colleagues, especially the Honorary Secretary, the Honorary Treasurer, Honorary Editors, Council Members, Associate Editors and the Staff Members of the Society for their unstinted support throughout the year.

The Convention of Chemists being an annual scientific endeavour of the Indian Chemical Society, we are meeting after a period of one year. Like all national symposia it travels from one place to another within the country. The present Convention is being held at the Nagarjuna University which is fortuitously associated with the name of Nagarjuna – a name which stands pre-eminent among Indian alchemists. As the President of the Society may I once again extend a very warm welcome to all of you who are present with us here this morning to participate in this inaugural meeting. I believe, most of you will actively participate in the scientific programme that will follow this meeting and make the Convention a success.

I have divided my address into two parts. The first part

titled "The Indian Chemical Society and its Journal" deals briefly with the establishment of the Indian Chemical Society and some of my introspections regarding the Society and its Journal. The second part dealing with certain chemical aspects of general interest will be presented after the break following the Inaugural Session.

I think this is perhaps the appropriate place to pay tribute to those whose prodigious scientific insight blended with nationalism and a long cherished dream gave birth to the Indian Chemical Society. I would like to give some facts in very brief about the genesis of the Society and its basic objectives, specially for the young scientists and Fellows who should feel proud of its heritage and now for being associated with it. A detailed history of the foundation of the Indian Chemical Society has been narrated¹ by Professor J. N. Mukherjee, the Founder Honorary Secretary of the Society. Professor J. C. Ghosh², Professor S. S. Bhatnagar³ and Professor N. R. Dhar⁴ also gave accounts of the background of the genesis of the Society. The state of affairs and the progress of the Society since its foundation on May 9, 1924 till 1932 have been enumerated by Dr. Bawa Kartar Singh in his Presidential Address⁵ delivered at the 9th AGM of the Society on January 3, 1933 at Patna. In this connection, the article⁶ entitled "Sixty Years of the Indian Chemical Society – its Growth and Development" published in the Society's Diamond Jubilee Souvenir giving much information may also be referred to.

Three outstanding personalities in chemical sciences of India, Dr. Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar, Dr. Jnan Chandra Ghosh, and Dr. Jnanendra Nath Mukherjee while doing research in London during 1920 realized that the chemical researches in India were rapidly increasing and that the *Journal of the Chemical Society* (London) was not able to publish, even their worthy research papers within a reasonable time. Imbued with the patriotic spirit of the day they conceived the idea of the establishment of the Indian Chemical Society with its own Journal. Immediately on their return from UK following discussions with many leading scientific personalities in several meetings held at different

[†]Part I of the Presidential Address delivered at the Inaugural Session of the 39th Annual Convention of Chemists held at Nagarjuna University, Nagarjunanagar, on December 23, 2002.

places of the country the Indian Chemical Society was established and registered as a corporate body on 9th May, 1924. The first Council of the Society was composed of the following celebrities in chemistry in India :

The Office-Bearers and the Members of the first Council in 1924¹

<i>President</i>	:	Sir P. C. Ray
<i>Vice-Presidents</i>	:	Dr. J. L. Simonsen Dr. Gilbert J. Fowler
<i>Honorary Secretary</i>	:	Dr. J. N. Mukherjee
<i>Honorary Treasurer</i>	:	Dr. P. C. Mitter
<i>Honorary Editors</i>	:	Dr. E. R. Watson Dr. N. R. Dhar
<i>Council Members :</i>		
Dr. S. S. Bhatnagar		Dr. H. E. Annett
Dr. Bawa K. Singh		Dr. B. B. Dey
Dr. A. R. Normand		Mr. B. H. Wilson
Dr. J. C. Ghosh		Dr. A. N. Meldrum
Dr. K. G. Naik		Mr. R. N. Sen
Dr. H. K. Sen		Dr. R. L. Datta

The office of the Society was maintained at the University of Calcutta, 92 Upper Circular Road, Calcutta, in the room of the Hony. Secretary. With years the Council has expanded (total Council Members 50 at present) and the number of Fellows has increased from initial 101 to nearly 2500 now. The quarterly Journal of the Society was first published in November, 1924. The Journal was elevated to a bimonthly one in 1928 and to a monthly one by 1930. The publication cost was borne initially by the University of Calcutta. Later on till 1933, the Society was allotted a space of about 12' × 10' in one corner of the Chemistry Department of the University of Calcutta and the space was naturally overcongested with no space for library or exchange journals. Through the donation of Rs. 10000 by Acharya P. C. Ray to the University of Calcutta, two large rooms (30' × 20') along with the verandah (40' × 10') were constructed in the third storey of the extension of the south wing of the University College of Science main building for the office and the library of the Society in 1933.

The Society had sufficient space till fifties but it is still continuing to be housed in the same space even after 70 years. In view of the expanding activities of the Society a suitable land (area about 10.5 kottah) in the heart of the city was acquired from the Calcutta Improvement Trust and the foundation-stone for the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Building for housing the Society was also laid by Professor J. N. Mukherjee in 1970. Unfortunately, the building construction could not be started as yet for fund scarcity. *As the President of the Society I earnestly appeal to all*

concerned for helping the Society to raise sufficient fund for the construction of the Building which will ensure tremendous enhancement of its varied activities, apart from the enrichment of the Society's Journal.

Of several activities of the Society, holding the Annual Convention and the publication of its journal are most vital. The Convention acts as a forum for interaction amongst senior and junior scientists, offers exposure to different types of chemistry that are going on in different laboratories of our country.

The Journal is the soul of the Society. Its health manifests the Society's health. In absence of adequate nourishment by way of getting good to best papers from our Fellows and eminent chemists, applied chemists and biochemists of India and abroad, the Journal can not elevate its standard upto the expectation. In the midst of various constraints mostly due to dirt of space, fund and good papers, the Society is caught up in an affair of controversy – specially regarding the standard of the Journal.

However, I hope that without contributing to the Journal people will refrain from nonconstructive criticism that provides fodder to the rumour mills that the Journal of the Society has a poor image. I beg an answer to a basic question from the substantial chemists of India – wherefrom will the wealth of the Journal come? *The Journal does not belong only to the Society or the contributors; being the premier chemical journal of India it belongs to the whole nation. I strongly believe that all the substantial chemists of our country are the true guardians of the Journal.* Their low enthusiasm for publishing papers in this Journal, unlike most of the countries where substantial works are published in their own Chemical Society's Journal, results in its eventual poor image. When we turn the search light inward, we find this cause and effect.

We know that the rate of growth of any corporate body can not remain the same during its existence; it must suffer ups and downs. We also have fallen in the same pattern but within our limited resources we could show our best. With the advent of computer, the offset printing process has been started replacing the age-old typeset printing process. A new era started when the first such computer-aided DTP-offset print Journal issue (April-May 1993 Special Issue) was published. The Special Issues of the Journal published during 1978-2002 are listed in Table 1. A cursory glance of the Commemoration Issues of the recent past (1997-2001) will convince one of our ability, and one will find them in no way inferior to the Journal issues of many chemical societies abroad. How it has been possible! We got original good papers and good reviews on invitation even from Nobel

Table 1. Special issues of the Journal published during 1978-2002

1978 – November issue (168 pages)	Professor (Mrs) Asima Chatterjee 60th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1979 – November issue (128 pages)	Professor S K Mukherjee 65th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1982 – February issue (210 pages)	Professor R C Mehrotra 60th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1982 – April issue (180 pages)	Professor N R Dhar 90th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1982 – December issue (286 pages)	Professor Arun K Dey 60th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1983 – December issue (148 pages)	Professor J N Mukherjee 90th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1984 – November–December joint issue (202 pages)	Professor Mahendra Kumar Rout 60th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1985 – November issue (130 pages) (first part)	December issue (182 pages) (second part) Diamond Jubilee Commemoration Issue
1986 – January issue (186 pages)	Professor Sadhan Basu 65th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1989 – August-October joint issue (240 pages)	Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray 125th Birth Anniversary Commemoration Issue
1992 – August issue (128 pages)	Professor D Banerjee 60th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1993 – April-May joint issue (216 pages)	Special Issue in honour of Professor S Aditya
1993 – November-December joint issue (220 pages)	Professor H L Nigam 65th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1994 – June-August joint issue (234 pages)	Professor D P Chakraborty 60th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1997 – November-December joint issue (188 pages)	Professor T R Govindachari 80th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1998 – October-December joint issue (322 pages)	Professor Sukh Dev 75th Birthday Commemoration Issue
1999 – November-December joint issue (252 pages)	Professor D Nasipuri 75th Birthday Commemoration Issue
2000 – November-December joint issue (196 pages)	Platinum Jubilee Commemoration Issue-I
2001 – October-December joint issue (320 pages)	Platinum Jubilee Commemoration Issue-II

Laureates, and the Society has shown its ability of publishing the Journal timely in a very presentable way. So if we get good papers throughout the year certainly the standard of our Journal will be elevated.

On analysis of Table 2 showing the number of papers received and published, and the number of printed pages year-wise during 1978-2002, the following facts emerge

- 1) Number of papers received has decreased significantly from '80s to '90s and thereafter
- 2) Less number of full papers (as evident from the number of printed pages) is being received during the last decade or so, compared to 80's and early 90's
- 3) Number of printed pages became minimum (pp 696) in the year 2000 in spite of the November-December Special Issue.
- 4) During the years 1997-2001, the numbers of printed pages would have been alarmingly less but for the Special Issues
- 5) The anomalies between the different columns are due to the high rate of rejection of poor papers as well as delay in acceptance.

Of course, the reduction in the number of printed pages is also due to the fact that the papers are being thoroughly edited and significantly condensed, wherever necessary, since the early 90's, moreover, DTP-offset printing using small fonts has also contributed to the reduction of pages

In view of the above, I fervently appeal to all the eminent chemists, biochemists and applied chemists of our country to publish the results of their findings in our national Journal and to patronise our Society in every respect

Of the fifteen Branches of the Society which have, so far, come into existence only four Branches, viz Magadh, Mumbai, Sagar and Vadodara are now actively functioning. The activities of the Mumbai Branch is worth emulating. This Branch has been working satisfactorily since its inception on April 29, 1926. I congratulate the Fellow Chemists of the Mumbai Branch on their remarkable work.

It would be in the interest of the parent Society as well as of the Branches that the Branches at Ahmedabad, Allahabad, Amritsar, Bhagalpur, Chennai, Delhi, Gawhati, Kurukshetra, Patna, Rajkot and Waltair get organized and become active again under the leadership of senior and experienced Fellows at each of these Branches. In fact, according to Dr Mata Prasad⁷, Branches should be "established in all the University towns and other places of chemical interest in India, not only the stature of the Society will be enhanced but the chemists in different parts of the country will be grouped together with bonds of chemical brotherhood". The required advantage of the cooperation of the Fellows of the Society can thus be gained by establishing more and more Branches.

It will be good for the Journal and the Society if the present and past Council Members, Associate Editors and

Table 2. Papers received, published (year-volume wise) during 1978-2002

Year (Vol. no.)	Total no. of papers received	Total no. of papers published	Total no. of printed pages of the Journal
1978 (55)	762	453	1370
1979 (56)	816	459	1328
1980 (57)	751	457	1300
1981 (58)	782	468	1272
1982 (59)	678	444	1494
1983 (60)	501	434	1258
1984 (61)	470	382	1124
1985 (62)	426	326	1106
1986 (63)	455	356	1130
1987 (64)	483	320	826
1988 (65)	627	367	940
1989 (66)	620	336	948
1990 (67)	518	414	1042
1991 (68)	582	300	702
1992 (69)	500	303	934
1993 (70)	550	256	1076
1994 (71)	373	169	798
1995 (72)	392	223	920
1996 (73)	330	205	722
1997 (74)	320	328	1014
1998 (75)	340	237	864
1999 (76)	363	205	766
2000 (77)	366	168	696
2001 (78)	430	170	818
2002 (79)	383	270	1007

the Branches take initiatives to persuade reputed chemists to communicate to the Journal at least once or twice a year and also to review papers. In this regard I may mention that a number of referees do not respond promptly causing delay in the acceptance of even good papers. I feel that efforts should be made to get relatively young established chemists (35-50 years) as referees who are expected to do the job joyfully. Of course, many papers without much scientific content and containing errors and incongruities are also received which need revision, causing delay or rejection.

On analysis it is evident that the authors have every reason for their unwillingness to publish in the Society's Journal. The policy of the people at the helms of the various apex bodies in academic domain compel the authors to stay away from their national journals. Assessment and evaluation of the scientific research papers are being judged primarily on the basis of the names of the journals having high impact

factor and not on their scientific contents. Even an inferior quality short paper/communication published in a foreign journal of higher impact factor usually gets preference to a reasonably good full paper published in the *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society* by the Committees for selection of candidates for jobs/scholarships/awards etc. As an Honorary Editor during 1997-2000 I had a sad experience of not getting papers from good chemists of our country (excepting for the commemoration issues) due to the reasons stated. I hereby make a passionate protest against the whole procedure of judgement, and request the pertinent authorities to give up their present traditional outlook showing the authors the way to reestablish their faith in the Journal of the Society. *Imbibed with a patriotic feeling let us anticipate a challenging future of our national Journal, and for that matter, of the entire Society; let us not defeat the purpose of the formation of the Society by our illustrious predecessors; let us enhance the prestige of our national Journal. Our efforts to improve the Society's condition in every respect will act as offerings to the memory of Acharya P. C. Ray and other great sons of India and to the fundamental theme of the Society.*

However, I am sure, the Society will remain ever memorable and lovable as the first-born child amongst the scientific societies of India.

Before I conclude, I acknowledge with thanks the assistance rendered by Mr. Prabir K. Gupta, the Executive Editor of the Society, in collecting the data regarding the Society's Journal.

Thank you all for your kind attention.

References

1. J. N. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 1175-1181 (Sir J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture, 1964).
2. J. C. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**, 465-478 (Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture delivered on August 2, 1950 at Calcutta).
3. S. S. Bhatnagar, Presidential Address, in the Section of Chemistry, delivered on January 4, 1928 in the 15th Indian Science Congress held at Calcutta: "Proceedings of the 15th Indian Science Congress", Calcutta, 1928, p. 105.
4. N. R. Dhar, "Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray: Life and Achievements", Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, 1972, pp. 47-49.
5. B. K. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **10**, 1-26.
6. "Indian Chemical Society Diamond Jubilee (1924-1984) Souvenir", Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, 1974, pp. 1-11.
7. M. Prasad, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **32**, 1 (Presidential Address delivered at the 31st Annual General Meeting of the Society at Baroda on January 4, 1975).